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APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DIGITALIZATION OF HUMAN RESOURCES

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Abstract

In a fierce competitive era, organizations have moved from traditional human resource management to digital human resource management for their survival and to be market leaders. Present days the companies are having competitive edge with the digital technologies from one another in order to dominate the business empire. To be global, companies are digitally transforming their human resource management. Innovations and advances in digital technology has made easier for HR manager to take decisions and manage the people. Companies are incorporating digital technology in order to transform their business. Digitalization of human resource management also reduces costs, improves the speed and quality of human resource processes. We are using technology to deliver human resource management activities. Digital work place can be created fully with the help of HR technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, robotics, cloud computing etc. The organizations have to identify the area of their opportunity to betterly work and efficiently use the HR tools.

The workplace of present days is infused with technology and systems. Digitalization processes now have come as angels for the companies which will help them to predict different aspects such as attrition, engagement level, retention and development of employees. The aim of this paper focuses on the application of artificial intelligence and digitalization of human resources with the objective to accelerate and withstand in a global competition of the companies.

Keywords: Collaboration, Resources, Application, Global, Development, Technology.

Introduction

A digital technology plays an important role in the lives of employees and human resource management. Digitalization poses many new challenges and opportunities to reshape their role and responsibilities to strategically driven. The greatest challenge for the managers is to identify the changes, groom, prepare them and connect with digital information and communication technologies. Due to innovations in computing and telecommunication

technologies the capacity of humans to store, transmit and manipulate information has expanded to a large extent. An innovative strategy can create more digital opportunities where companies can position as a market leader. Human Resource strategy enables the employees to learn and grow and develops amazing talent among them. A strategic plan has to be developed in order to increase company value and performance and should be integrated with technology. HRD professional should focus more on retaining workforce and also keeping them actively engaged even in times of mass retrenchments and economic slowdown. Employees are to be recruited, developed, compensated and then integrated in an organized manner so, as to give their best to the organizations.

The new technologies are reshaping employee skills, experience and enabling greater integration and flexibility by building innovative human strategies. With the help of new technologies the repetitive task will be streamlined and efficiency can be increased as the firm can concentrate on problem solving and learning activities.

Present days are the age of artificial intelligence which has predominated the world and used by various professionals and disciplines to foster their growth. Due to the use of HR technologies the physical barriers has come down. The organizations are transforming themselves with the collaborations and communicating by using artificial intelligence. According to Donald Sothorn, Artificial Intelligence helps in handling recruitment process, retention of employees and also increased productivity more efficiently than traditional human resources methods.

Though human resource is very difficult to control, if it is utilized efficiently gives outstanding results and adds value to the business. Human resource is the power of the organization. Among all, human resources are one of the important resources in managing stakeholders with the help of artificial intelligence. Josh Bersin in an article, “How will Artificial Intelligence in HR be a game-changer”? explained that Artificial Intelligence based tools are transforming human resource processes and eliminating human errors. According to him Artificial Intelligence does the following functions such as HR screening, reading documents, to interpret, selecting prospective candidates through video based interviews. Companies can tap inherent potential and retain them for a longer time. Managing HR data properly and efficiently is one of the major threats to the company and also a challenge that is posed to the human resource department. Digitalization involves new organizational processes as well as changes in artifacts themselves. To lead digitalization initiatives, expertise is needed and the required tools and technology to be adequate. With the help of messaging, team communication and collaboration has become easier for keeping employees in touch of information.

Need of the Artificial Intelligence

Many disciplines such as electronics, electrical, mechanical, marketing, agriculture and bio-technology where Artificial Intelligence is adopted. Artificial Intelligence has already penetrated into the leading sectors like banking, medical, telecommunication, healthcare, pharmaceuticals and information technology, transportation, education, advertising, film

industry, legal services and insurance sectors for assistance and development of the organizations. Embracing artificial intelligence is the key for success of the organizations and to digitally transform themselves. There is a need to study and to do research of Artificial intelligence in human resources field. To provide solutions to the organizations as they have to struggle in terms of managing cost, quality, innovation etc. The present paper discuss about the Artificial Intelligence in different purposes related to Human Resources in companies.

Artificial Intelligence in Human Resources

Delays in hiring and recruitment of human resources can be reduced due to use of artificial intelligence. The HR software tools are designed in such a way that it analyzes, gather information and identify candidates. Through artificial intelligence the following functions of human resource department can be done.

1. Recruitment

Using human resource tools help the companies to save lot of time, money and energy. The cost of poor hiring and wrong decisions can be avoided. The human resource tool helps in reading, interpreting, translating and scanning the applications applied for jobs.

2. Training

The planning, organizing, learning and training of the employees can be done effectively by the use of digital technologies applied by the organizations. Today, in the age of online courses, video-conferencing and webinars, companies which are applying the human resource tools for digitalization process are successfully competing with other and also giving required knowledge to the employees in handling their jobs. Social tools such as whatsapp, facebook, linkedin, twitter etc., playing an important role in training the employees.

3. Employee Engagement and Performance Appraisal

Engaging employees is one of the biggest and difficult tasks for an organization. Constant monitoring their behavior is also a big challenge in these days. By using human resource tools such as artificial intelligence gives better results. It also helps in improving productivity and boosts the engagement of employees in a proper way.

4. Retention

Retaining the talented employees can be done with the help of artificial intelligence in an effective way. The tool helps in identifying the efficient and hardworking employees, so that they can be retain the skilled people in a right manner.

The workplace can be more efficient, vibrant, thrilling and employees will be highly dedicated to work if we bring artificial intelligence into human resources for doing speedy work. In today's world artificial intelligence has become the reality. As the activities of human resources are digitally transforming, companies has to catch up to the expectations of the

employees and customers in order to prosper and be in the competition. The google company is using next generation artificial intelligence training system. According to Nick Stat, google organization uses technologies to improve google translate, google photos and software etc.,

Conclusion

As the world is becoming more complex, dynamic and increasingly uncertain the digitalization process helps the companies in reaching their goals. The present days with the help of Artificial Intelligence the company can engage the candidate either before or after they apply for a job in the companies. Re-engagement can also be done with the help of artificial intelligence to update candidate to learn new positions, work experiences. In the present days, the technology has completely redefined the role of human resources. It is mechanizing huge task that employees are doing to improve their work process. With the application of artificial intelligence in human resources an immense amount of time can be saved. By application of artificial intelligence in organizations, administrative work of the managers will be saved for doing repetitive work. In this way it can make a huge difference and artificial intelligence will be a game changer. Artificial intelligence is extending human capability and performance in the companies.

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